

Bengal), Bihar, and Andhra Pradesh. Mean grain yield over 5 locations was 4.4 t/ha and was more than that of check variety Tilakkachari (2.9 t/ha). At Arundhutinagar, it yielded around 6 t/ha. The water level varied from 40 to 70 cm in

the test locations (Table 1).

CN505-5-32-9 is photoperiod sensitive and flowers the first week of Nov when day length is 11 h 50 min. It has stiff culms and moderate elongation capacity, and is 110 cm tall when grown in shallow

water, but can elongate to 138 cm in deep water (Table 2).

CN505-5-32-9 produces 250 panicles/m² and long bold, white grains. The 1,000-grain weight is 24.8 g. It is resistant to bacterial leaf blight and brown spot. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

Pant Dhan 4, a medium-maturing rice variety for irrigated lands

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Pant Dhan 4, a medium-maturing, dwarf (93 cm) rice variety was released recently in U. P. for cultivation in irrigated fields. It was developed in Sri Lanka from the cross IR262/Remadja and tested in the International Rice Observational Nursery as BG90-2 in 1974. The plants have good tillering capacity, mature in 126-132 d, and have high yield potential. Grains are long, slender, and translucent, with good cooking quality. It is moderately resistant to bacterial leaf blight and will be a good substitute for Jaya, which has become susceptible.

Pant Dhan 4 was tested in station trials from 1976 to 1980 and in state variety trials from 1979 to 1982 (see table). □

Performance of Pant Dhan 4 in state variety trials in Uttar Pradesh, India.

Trial centers	Grain yield (t/ha)		CD at 5%	CV in 5%	Days to maturity	
	Pant Dhan 4	Jaya			Pant Dhan 4	Jaya
<i>1981 kharif</i>						
Azamgarh	4.6	4.6	0.1	1.8	134	131
Bareilly	7.0	6.7	0.2	2.1	133	141
Haldwani	7.2	5.4	1.2	12.4	139	143
Hardoi	4.1	4.3	0.2	4.3	124	135
Mathura	5.1	4.8	0.3	4.5	123	130
Meerut	2.0	1.7	0.3	12.6	140	141
Jhansi	2.1	2.5	0.6	16.1	123	127
Barabanki	3.2	3.6	0.4	7.9	122	129
Etawah	3.1	4.3	1.0	20.6	122	126
Varanasi	3.1	3.5	1.5	12.0	110	126
Average	4.2	4.2	—	—	126	133
<i>1982 kharif</i>						
Azamgarh	3.8	4.5	0.09	1.73	131	133
Bareilly	5.9	5.6	0.07	0.75	132	139
Haldwani	5.8	5.5	0.9	9.8	152	154
Hardoi	4.8	4.7	0.3	5.3	130	138
Mathura	4.3	4.6	0.2	3.2	115	128
Meerut	6.3	4.5	1.0	10.8	139	139
Jhansi	5.6	4.7	N.S.	22.2	129	137
Barabanki	—	—	—	—	—	—
Etawah	—	—	—	—	—	—
Varanasi	—	—	—	—	—	—
Average	5.2	4.9	—	—	132	138

Variation of ripening periods among rice genotypes

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Most of the photosynthates accumulated as grain yield are formed from anthesis to senescence. Little information is available on the extent of variation in this duration. We sought to define ripening period for rice genotypes with a wide range of maturity duration. The entries were from

Vegetative and grain ripening periods in days for different rice types, Almora, India.

Duration	Genotypes (no.)	Duration (d)			
		Preanthesis		Postanthesis	
		Mean	Range	Mean	Range
Short	20	80	65-87	37	20-43
Medium	45	96	88-105	36	30-44
Medium-long	22	100	106-114	40	33-48
Long	4	120	115-125	37	28-45

different rice growing regions and included some local hill collections. Entries were transplanted in irrigated fields on 15

Jul 1981 and 1982 at Almora, at 1,600 m above sea level. Of an initial 100 entries, 9 were dropped because they did not

flower normally. Data were recorded for primary tillers when anthesis began and when 75% of the florets showed glume senescence.

Entries flowered between the third week of Aug and the first week of Oct. Preanthesis phase ranged from 65 to 125 d (see table). Average period from anthesis to glume senescence (ripening period) varied from 28 to 48 d. Ripening period was not related to length of pre-anthesis period ($r = -0.10$), and the dif-

ferent maturity groups had similar ranges.

Short-duration cultures flowered the last 2 wk of Aug when average temperatures were relatively higher (23.0°C).

Long-duration entries flowered the first week of Oct when average temperatures were lower (17.5°C). The similar range of durations among genotypes of the two groups indicates that the observed variation was not caused by temperature differences and is in fact a varietal character.

Genotypes with short ripening dura-

tion (around 30 d) were Daegaldo and Heug-Jodo (early); Jodo, Mujudo, and Deog-Jeog-Jodo (medium); Kaoshang 27, IR9202-23-2, IAC25, China 988, and Thapuli (medium-long); and C21 and China 4 (long). Long ripening period (around 40 d) was recorded for L 100-A, Nancee, K333, and Kitakogan (early); JC99, IR80-102, Khonorullo, Barmi, and Eiko (medium); Chinan 2, Tapuno, Norin 18, VL 8, and Taichung 176 (medium-long); and Kalimpong (late). □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Reaction of several rice varieties to rice tungro virus (RTV) complex

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The presence of RTV complex in non-IR varieties with different reactions to tungro infection and to its vector, green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*, was determined by latex test using antisera to rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). Eleven-day-old seedlings were mass-inoculated with an average of five tungro-viruliferous insects per seedling. Only plants that exhibited tungro-like symptoms were included in this test.

We also studied the effect of an increased number of viruliferous insects per seedling on RTV complex infection in five resistant varieties: Gam Pai 30-12-15, Pankhari 203, Habiganj DW8, Utri Rajapan, and ARC1 1554. In a screen cage, the seedlings were mass-inoculated with 25 viruliferous GLH/seedling for 3 h with TN1 as the virus source. Healthy TN1 seedlings with one insect per seedling in test tubes were inoculated simultaneously with viruliferous insects taken from this colony. All inoculated plants were evaluated using the latex test.

Results indicated that RTBV and RTSV were generally present in varieties with susceptible and intermediate reactions to

Table 1. Presence of RTBV and RTSV as detected by the latex test in non-IR varieties mass-inoculated by an average of 5 insects/seedling, IRRI.

Variety	Reaction to		Plants tested (no.)	Plants (no.) that reacted to the presence of			Plants (no.) with no reaction
	GLH ^a	RTV ^b		RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	
Gam Pai 30-12-15	R	R	21	0	16	0	5
ARC11554	R	R	11	1	9	0	1
Pankhari 203	MR	R	20	1	16	0	3
Habiganj DW8	MS	R	12	1	11	0	0
Utri Rajapan	MS	R	19	11	8	0	0
Bremli	S	I	22	22	0	0	0
KU115	S	I	19	19	0	0	0
R21	S	I	25	25	0	0	0
Tosidongi	S	I	12	10	2	0	0
Liao-Feng 4	S	I	16	5	11	0	0
Naylamp	MR	S	18	12	6	0	0
ARC5929	S	S	8	8	0	0	0
63-83	S	S	20	19	0	0	1
AUS 100	-	S	18	18	0	0	0
Kuatik Putih	MR	S	24	24	0	0	0
TN1 (check)	S	S	24	21	3	0	0

^a Data from IRRI Entomology Department. ^b Greenhouse mass screening results, IRRI Plant Pathology Department: 0-30% infection = resistant (R), 31-40% = intermediate (I), 60-100% = susceptible (S).

Table 2. Presence of RTBV and RTSV as detected by latex test in resistant non-IR varieties mass-inoculated by an average of 25 insects/seedling, IRRI.

Variety	Plants tested (no.)	Plants (no.) that reacted to the presence of			Plants (no.) with no reaction
		RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	
Gam Pai 30-12-15	21	1	8	0	12
Pankhari 203	21	0	8	0	13
Habiganj DW8	35	0	19	0	16
Utri Rajapan	32	6	12	1	13
ARC11554	41	0	14	0	27
TN1 ^a (check)	19	16	2	0	1

^a Inoculated in test tube at one insect per seedling.